

Mildly β -Normal Spaces and $rg\beta$ -Continuous Functions

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Abstract: *The aim this paper is to introduce and study a new class of spaces, called mildly β -normal spaces. The relationship among normal, almost normal, quasi normal, mildly normal, π -normal spaces and their generalizations are investigated. Moreover, we introduce $rg\beta$ -continuous functions. Utilizing $rg\beta$ -continuity, we obtain characterization and preservation theorems for mildly β -normal spaces.*

Keywords: β -open, β -normal, mildly β -normal spaces, $g\beta$ -closed and $rg\beta$ -closed function.

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1. Introduction

The notion of quasi normal space was introduced by Zaitsev [25]. The concept of almost normality was introduced by Singal and Arya [20]. The notion of mildly normal space was introduced by Shchepin [19] and Singal and Singal [22] independently. Nour [4] introduced a weaker form of normality, called p -normality and obtained their properties. Mahmoud et al. [7] introduced the notion of β -normal spaces and obtained their characterizations and preservation theorems. Dontchev and Noiri [4] introduce the notion of πg -closed sets as a weak form of g -closed sets due to Levine [6]. By using πg -closed sets, Dontchev and Noiri [8] obtained a new characterization of quasi normal spaces. π -normal topological space was introduced by Kalantan [5]. M. C. Sharma and Hamant Kumar [17] introduced a weaker form of normality, called $\pi\beta$ -normality and obtained their properties. The notion of quasi β -normal and mildly β -normal spaces were introduced by M. C. Sharma and Hamant Kumar [16]. Thabit and Kamaraulhaili [24] introduced a new type of normality, called πp -normality and obtained their characterizations. The concept of quasi p -normality was introduced by Thabit and Kamaraulhaili [23]. The notion of almost p -normal and mildly p -normal spaces were introduced by G. B. Navalagi [10]. The notion of almost β -normal space was introduced by M. C. Sharma and Hamant Kumar [18].

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, τ) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** (resp. **regular closed**) if $A = int(cl(A))$ (resp. $A = cl(int(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open**. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**. A is said to be **β -open** [1] if $A \subset cl(int(cl(A)))$, **preopen** [9] (briefly **p -open**) if $A \subset int(cl(A))$. The

complement of a β -open (resp. p -open) set is said to be **β -closed** [1] (resp. **p -closed** [9]). The intersection of all β -closed (resp. p -closed) sets containing A is called **β -closure** [2] (resp. **p -closure** [9]) of A , and is denoted by $\beta cl(A)$ (resp. $pcl(A)$). The **β -Interior** [2] of A , denoted by $\beta int(A)$, is defined as union of all β -open sets contained in A .

2.1 Definition

A subset A of a space (X, τ) is said to be

- 1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g -closed**) [6] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.
- 2) **regular generalized closed** (briefly **rg -closed** [14]) if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- 3) **generalized preclosed** (briefly **gp -closed**) [8] if $pcl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is open in X .
- 4) **regular generalized preclosed** (briefly **rgp -closed**) [11] if $pcl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- 5) **generalized β -closed** (briefly **$g\beta$ -closed**) [3] if $\beta cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is open in X .
- 6) **regular generalized β -closed** (briefly **$rg\beta$ -closed**) [15] if $\beta cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- 7) **g -open** (resp. **rg -open**, **gp -open**, **rgp -open**, **$g\beta$ -open**, **$rg\beta$ -open**) if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. rg -closed, gp -closed, rgp -closed, $g\beta$ -closed, $rg\beta$ -closed).

2.2 Remark

We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.3 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g -closed but not closed.

2.4 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is gpr -closed as well as $rg\beta$ -closed. But it is not rg -closed.

2.5 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is gpr -closed as well as $rg\beta$ -closed. But it is neither gp -closed nor p -closed.

2.6 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then, $A = \{a\}$ is p -closed as well as β -closed. But it is not rg -closed.

2.7 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is $g\beta$ -closed as well as $rg\beta$ -closed. But it is neither g -closed nor closed.

2.8 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is β -closed as well as $g\beta$ -closed but it is not closed.

2.9 Lemma

A subset A of a space X is $rg\beta$ -open if and only if $F \subset \beta \text{int}(A)$ whenever F is a regular closed and $F \subset A$.

3. Mildly β -Normal Spaces

3.1 Definition

A topological space X is said to be **quasi β -normal** [16] (resp. **quasi-normal** [25], **quasi p -normal** [23]) if for every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets H, K , there exist disjoint β -open (resp. open, p -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

3.2 Definition

A topological space X is said to be **mildly β -normal** [20] (resp. **mildly-normal** [19, 22], **mildly p -normal** [10]) if for every pair of disjoint regular closed subsets H, K , there exist disjoint β -open (resp. open, p -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

3.3 Definition

A topological space X is said to be **$\pi\beta$ -normal** [17] (resp. **π -normal** [5], **πp -normal** [24]) if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed, there exist

disjoint β -open (resp. open, p -open) sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.4 Definition

A topological space X is said to be **almost β -normal** [18] (resp. **almost normal** [20], **almost p -normal** [10]) if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is regular closed, there exist disjoint β -open (resp. open, p -open) sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.5 Definition

A topological space X is said to be **β -normal** [7] (resp. **p -normal** [13]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint β -open (resp. p -open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.6 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, τ) is almost p -normal space, but it is not p -normal, since the pair of disjoint closed sets $\{b\}$ and $\{c\}$ have no disjoint p -open sets containing them.

3.7 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint closed subsets of X are $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$. Also $U = \{a, b\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ are β -open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence X is β -normal but it is not normal.

3.8 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, τ) is quasi p -normal space, but it is not p -normal.

3.9 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint closed subsets of X are $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$. Also $U = \{a, b\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ are p -open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence (X, τ) is p -normal but it is not normal.

3.10 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, τ) is almost normal but it is not normal.

3.11 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, τ) is p -normal space because the only closed sets in X are X and \emptyset . But it is not p -normal, since the pair of disjoint closed sets $\{b\}$ and $\{c\}$ have no disjoint p -open sets containing them.

By the definitions and examples stated above, we have the following diagram:

3.12 Theorem

The following are equivalent for a space X:

- 1) X is mildly β -normal.
- 2) For any disjoint regular closed sets A and B, there exist disjoint $g\beta$ -open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$
- 3) For any disjoint regular closed sets A and B of X, there exist disjoint $rg\beta$ -open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.
- 4) For any regular closed set A and any regular open set V containing A, there exists a $g\beta$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \beta\text{cl}(U) \subset V$.
- 5) For any regular closed set A and any regular open set V containing A, there exists a $rg\beta$ -open set U of X such that $A \subset U \subset \beta\text{cl}(U) \subset V$.

Proof

(1) \Rightarrow (2), (2) \Rightarrow (3), (3) \Rightarrow (4), (4) \Rightarrow (5) and (5) \Rightarrow (1).

(1) \Rightarrow (2). Let X be mildly β -normal space. Let A, B be disjoint regular closed sets of X. By assumption, there exist disjoint β -open sets U, V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Since every β -open set is $g\beta$ -open, so, U and V are $g\beta$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3). Let A, B be two disjoint regular closed sets. By assumption, there exist $g\beta$ -open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Since $g\beta$ -open set is $rg\beta$ -open, so, U and V are $rg\beta$ -open such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(3) \Rightarrow (4). Let A be any regular closed set and V be any regular open set containing A. By assumption, there exist $rg\beta$ -open sets U and W such that $A \subset U$ and $X - V \subset W$. By **Lemma 2.9**, we get $X - V \subset \beta\text{int}(W)$ and $U \cap \beta\text{int}(W) = \emptyset$. Therefore, we obtain $\beta\text{cl}(U) \cap \beta\text{int}(W) = \emptyset$ and hence $A \subset U \subset \beta\text{cl}(U) \subset X - \beta\text{int}(W) \subset V$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5). Let A be any regular-closed set and V be any regular-open set containing A. By assumption, there exist $g\beta$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \beta\text{cl}(U) \subset V$. Since, every $g\beta$ -open set is $rg\beta$ -open, there exist $rg\beta$ -open sets U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \beta\text{cl}(U) \subset V$.

(5) \Rightarrow (1). Let A, B be any two disjoint regular-closed sets of X. Then $H \subset X - K$ and $X - B$ is regular-open. By assumption, there exists $rg\beta$ -open set G of X such that $A \subset G \subset \beta\text{cl}(G) \subset X - B$. Put $U = \beta\text{int}(G)$, $V = K - \beta\text{cl}(G)$. Then

U and V are disjoint β -open sets of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

Using **Theorem 3.12**, it is easy to show the following theorem, which is a Urysohn's Lemma version for mild β -normality. A proof can be established by a similar way of the normal case.

3.13 Theorem

A space X is mildly β -normal if and only if for every pair of disjoint regularly closed sets A and B of X, there exists a continuous function f on X into $[0, 1]$, with its usual topology, such that $f(A) = \{0\}$ and $f(B) = \{1\}$.

It is easy to see that the inverse image of a regularly closed set under an open continuous function is regularly closed. We will use that in the next theorem.

3.14 Theorem

Let X is a mildly β -normal space and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an open continuous injective function. Then $f(X)$ is a softly normal space.

Proof. Let A and B be any two regularly closed subset of $f(X)$ such that $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ regularly closed sets of X. Since X is mildly β -normal, there are two disjoint β -open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$. Since f is 1-1 and open, since every open set is β -open set, result follows.

3.15 Corollary

Mild β -normality is a topological property.

3.16 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- 1) **$rg\beta$ -continuous** if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $rg\beta$ -closed in X for every closed set F of Y.
- 2) **β - $rg\beta$ -continuous** if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $rg\beta$ -closed in X for every β -closed set F of Y.
- 3) **$rg\beta$ -irresolute** if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $rg\beta$ -closed in X for every $rg\beta$ -closed set F of Y.
- 4) **rc-preserving [12]** (resp. **almost closed [21]**) if $f(F)$ is regular closed (resp. closed) in Y for every regular closed set F of X.

3.17 Theorem

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a β -rg β -continuous, rc-preserving injection and Y is mildly β -normal then X is mildly β -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint regular closed sets of X . Since f is an rc-preserving injection, $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint regular closed sets of Y . By mild β -normality of Y , there exist disjoint β -open sets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$ and $f(B) \subset V$. Since f is β -rg β -continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ and $f^{-1}(V)$ are disjoint rg β -open sets containing A and B respectively. Hence by **Theorem 3.12** X is mildly β -normal.

3.18 Theorem

If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a β -rg β -continuous, almost closed surjection and Y is β -normal space, then X is mildly β -normal.

Proof. Similar to previous one.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced a new class of spaces, called mildly β -normal spaces and established their relationships with some weak forms of normal spaces like normal, almost normal, quasi normal, mildly normal, π -normal spaces and their generalizations in topological spaces.

References

[1] M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, S. N. EI Deeb and R. A. Mohamoud, β -open sets and β -continuous mappings, Bull. Fac. Assiut Univ. Sci., **12**(1983), 77-90.
 [2] M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, R. A. Mahmoud, and E. R. Lashin, β - closure and β -interior, J. Fac. Edu. Ain Shams Univ., **10**(1986), 235.
 [3] J. Dontchev, On generalizing semi- preopen sets, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. (Math.), **16** (1995), 35.
 [4] J. Dontchev and T. Noiri, Quasi-normal spaces and π_g -closed sets, Acta Math. Hungar. **89**(3)(2000), 211-219.
 [5] L. N. Kalantan, π -normal topological spaces, Filomat **22**:1 (2008), 173-181.
 [6] N. Levine, Generalized closed sets in topology, Rend. Circ. Mat. Palermo (2), **19**(1970), 89-96.
 [7] R. A. Mahmoud and M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, β -irresolute and β -topological invariant, Proc. Pakistan Acad. Sci., **27**(1990), 285.
 [8] H. Maki, J. Umehara and T. Noiri, Every topological space is pre- $T_{1/2}$, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser. A Math. **17**(1996), 33-42.
 [9] A. S. Mashhour, M. E. Abd EI-Monsef and S. N. EI-Deeb, On precontinuous and weak precontinuous mappings, Proc. Math. Phys. Soc. Egypt, **53**(1982), 47-53.
 [10] G. B. Navalagi, P-normal, Almost p-normal and mildly p-normal spaces, (Communicated).
 [11] T. Noiri, Almost p-regular spaces and some functions, Acta Math. Hungar., **79**(1998), 207-216.
 [12] T. Noiri, Mildly normal spaces and some functions, Kyungpook Math. J. **36**(1996), 183-190.
 [13] T. M. Nour, contribution to the Theory of Bitopological spaces, Ph. D. Thesis, Delhi Univ., 1989.

[14] N. Palaniappan and K. C. Rao, Regular generalized closed sets, Kyungpook Math. J., **33**(1993), 211-219.
 [15] Y. Palaniappan, On regular generalized β -closed sets, Int. J. of Sci. and Eng. Research, Vol. 4, 4(2013), 1410-1415.
 [16] M. C. Sharma and H. Kumar, Quasi β -normal spaces and $\pi_g\beta$ -closed functions, Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XXXVIII, **1**(2012), 149-153.
 [17] M. C. Sharma and H. Kumar, $\pi\beta$ -normal spaces, Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XXXVI, **4**(2010), 611-615.
 [18] M. C. Sharma and H. Kumar, Almost β -normal and some functions, (Communicated)
 [19] E. V. Shchepin, Real functions and near normal spaces, Sibirskii Mat. Zhurnal, **13**(1972), 1182-1196.
 [20] M. K. Singal and S. P. Arya, Almost normal and almost completely regular spaces, Glasnik Matematički, Tom 5(25) No. 1 (1970).
 [21] M. K. Singal and A. R. Singal, Almost continuous mappings, Yokohama Math. J., **16**(1968), 63-73.
 [22] M. K. Singal and A. R. Singal, Mildly normal spaces, Kyungpook Math. J., **13**(1973), 27-31.
 [23] S. A. S. Thabit and H. Kamaruihaili, On quasi p-normality spaces, Int. Journal of Math. Anal., **6**(27) (2012), 1301-1311.
 [24] S. A. S. Thabit and H. Kamaruihaili, πp -normality on topological spaces, Int. J. Math. Anal., **6**(21) (2012), 1023-1033.
 [25] V. Zaitsev, On certain classes of topological spaces and their biocompactifications, Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR, **178**(1968), 778-779.